

Extended volatile range PTR-MS setup for real-time puff-by-puff analysis of electronic nicotine delivery systems

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Abstract

The popularity of Electronic Nicotine Delivery Systems (ENDS) has led to an increase in interest in characterising the aerosol produced by these devices. So far, most published studies utilise traditional offline methods (e.g. GC-MS) which only give information on the average concentrations / amounts of compounds delivered by ENDS over a series of puffs. In order to be able to carry out detailed studies, there is a high demand for scientific data obtained with online methods that allow true puff-by-puff analysis. Proton Transfer Reaction – Time-Of-Flight – Mass Spectrometry (PTR-TOF-MS) with its real-time quantification capability is well-established in food and flavour science and therefore ideally suited for this task. However, there are several difficulties to overcome, for example the enormous concentration differences between the mainstream aerosol and the residual compounds in exhaled breath and the highly condensable nature of the aerosol, leading to extended retention times in mass spectrometric devices.

Here, we present a newly developed PTR-TOF-MS multipurpose sampling setup with a well-defined three-stage dilution system that can shift the instrument's dynamic range by more than four orders of magnitude. All surfaces that come in contact with the sample air are specially coated and heated to considerably reduce retention effects. We show results from a proof-of-concept study on exhaled air before, during and after the use of an ENDS. Our results demonstrate the ability of our system to perform highly time-resolved puff-by-puff characterisation of ENDS mainstream aerosol as well as in exhaled breath after ENDS consumption.

Keywords: ENDS, PTR-MS, real-time, puff-by-puff analysis, breath analysis

Introduction

Electronic devices that deliver nicotine via inhalation have been introduced already in the 1960s [1] and are nowadays commonly known as electronic cigarettes, e-cigarettes, electronic vaping devices or Electronic Nicotine Delivery Systems (ENDS). However, they were only successfully commercialised in the early 2000s [2]. Especially in the last decade, ENDS have achieved widespread use [3, 4]. It seems understandable that the rapid growth of the ENDS market increased the attention of the public, the media and regulatory authorities [5], particularly as ENDS have often been promoted as a safer alternative to conventional tobacco cigarettes because no combustion products are inhaled [6]. However, a systematic review of the existing literature on the health effects of ENDS shows that no firm statements can be made about the safety of ENDS [7] and that there is a lack of online data during product consumption, particularly on puff-by-puff variations. This is because mostly offline methods are used where, for example, the subjects exhale into a Tedlar bag immediately after smoking or vaping [8] and the contents of the bags are subsequently analysed.

One of the first studies using Proton Transfer Reaction - Mass Spectrometry (PTR-MS) to investigate exhaled air was conducted as early as 1995 to investigate time-dependent concentrations of benzene and acetonitrile in the breath of smokers and non-smokers [10]. In 2009, the advantages of using PTR in combination with Time-Of-Flight (TOF) analysers instead of quadrupole mass filters for online breath analysis were demonstrated [11]. In the context of e-cigarettes, the nicotine retention time of e-cigarette aerosols inhalation was determined by GC coupled with a flame ionisation detector and PTR-TOF-MS. Since the total Volatile Organic Compound (VOC) concentration was higher than the upper limit of the dynamic range of the PTR-TOF-MS device, a single-stage dilution system was developed [5]. More recently, a two-stage dilution system has been used to investigate both mainstream aerosols and exhaled breath [12]. The two-stage dilution system was necessary to achieve coverage of the concentration ranges in these two scenarios. With the growing interest in this field and the increasing demand for high-end studies, some shortcomings in this setup have become apparent.

Herein we present a proof-of-concept study of a fundamentally revised experimental setup to directly quantify the high concentrations in the ENDS mainstream aerosol of up to 10,000 ppmv as well as pptv-level concentrations in exhaled air tens of minutes after product use.

Experimental

In this study, we employed a PTR-TOF 6000 X2 (IONICON Analytik GmbH, Innsbruck, Austria). The technical specifications of this instrument are: Limit of Detection (LOD) < 10 pptv (1 s integration time), sensitivity > 2000 cps/ppbv, response time < 100 ms, mass resolution > 6000 m/Δm [13]. Details on the components and principles of PTR-MS instruments as well as established fields of application have already been described in detail in the book by Ellis and Mayhew [14]. In principle, the apparatus consists of two main parts, the ionisation section, where VOCs are ionised by chemical ionisation, and the detection section, where the ionised species are analysed according to their mass-to-charge (m/z) ratio by means of TOF-MS. The PTR-TOF 6000 X2 is equipped with the recently introduced Extended Volatility Range (EVR) technology [16]. That is, the inlet line and the PTR reaction region, and in general all other surfaces that come in contact with the sample air, are covered with a sophisticated coating and heated, avoiding any cold spots.

Although this instrument is equipped with Selective Reagent Ion Mass Spectrometry (SRI-MS) technology, which allows the use of H_3O^+ , NO^+ , O_2^+ , Kr^+ , and NH_4^+ as primary ions, we only use H_3O^+ ions for this proof-of-concept study.

Concentration calibration

Based on basic principles of ion chemistry and certain approximations, PTR-MS allows quantification without external calibration for most compounds [14]. The two main constituents of e-liquids used in ENDS, Propylene Glycol (PG, $\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$) and (Vegetable) Glycerol (VG, $\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$), are among the very few molecules that show strong fragmentation in soft PTR ionisation. Thus, we used a liquid calibration unit (LCU, IONICON Analytik GmbH, Innsbruck, Austria [15]) to transfer aqueous solutions of PG and VG in well-defined concentrations into the gas phase and carefully calibrated the instrument. Additionally, a calibration measurement was carried out for the e-liquid constituent nicotine ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2$). However, since nicotine nearly exclusively forms the protonated molecule after PTR from H_3O^+ , the calibrated results showed excellent agreement with the calculated values, thus confirming the initiatory statement.

Sampling setup

Figure 1: Schematic view of the newly developed PTR-TOF-MS multipurpose sampling setup (see text for details).

Based on the experiences obtained with a previous sampling setup [12], we constructed a completely revised sampling setup to enable comprehensive ENDS studies with extremely high time resolution and thus the possibility of online puff-by-puff analysis of mainstream aerosols as well as exhaled breath with a single PTR-MS instrument (see Figure 1). The novel inlet system consists of three main parts:

(i) A port for connecting a common smoking machine. With such a device, standardised puff volumes, durations and profiles can be selected. Thus, puff-by-puff variations of the constituents of mainstream aerosol can be analysed in real time.

(ii) An inhalation interface to quantify the actual concentrations of compounds during consumption of ENDS. That is, the subject inhales *ad libitum* via the interface connected to any ENDS.

(iii) An exhaled breath interface. After using an ENDS, the exhaled breath can be analysed to monitor metabolic processes in the human body and retention rates of inhaled or mouth-held compounds.

The new dilution system can achieve dilution rates up to 1:30,000 via a fully electronically controlled three-stage dilution, which provides high sample gas flow rates in all stages for improved response times. Furthermore, all surfaces that come into contact with sample air (dilution system, sample gas lines, EVR PTR-TOF-MS instrument [16]) are specially coated in order to prevent adsorption effects already at moderate temperatures (120°C).

Results and discussion

PTR-TOF-MS enables the acquisition of a complete mass spectrum with high mass resolution and time resolution and therefore the identification of a wide range of VOCs. The integration time in our experiments was 0.5 s for each data point. Three of the most common constituents present in ENDS aerosol are VG, PG and nicotine. Particularly gaseous VG and nicotine are known for their condensable or "sticky" nature causing memory effects and thus pose a challenge for online analysis techniques. As nicotine is present in detectable concentrations (pptv range) only in exhalations immediately following inhaling the ENDS aerosol, the results are not shown here.

Figure 2: Concentration (in ppbv) as a function of time (in s) for glycerol (VG) and propylene glycol (PG) in the top and bottom row, respectively. Four different time-frames were chosen: (A, blue background) prior to and (B, red background) immediately following inhalation of ENDS aerosol, (C, yellow background) immediately after stopping the use of ENDS and (D, green background) approximately one hour after the last inhalation of an ENDS. The red dots indicate average values of concentration of respective exhalations. See text for further explanations.

Figure 2 shows the results of the proof-of-concept study for concentrations of VG and PG (in ppbv) in the top and bottom rows, respectively, as a function of time (in s). Note that the scale of the y-axes varies for each panel, while the time range is the same for each column for better comparability of relative VG and PG concentrations in exhaled air. In addition, an average value for each exhalation is indicated by a red dot. This value was determined as an average value within the time window where the concentration is always above 20% of the maximum concentration of the corresponding exhaled breath. The value of 20% was chosen to be clearly above the background noise.

In order to obtain "blank" concentrations, the test subject first exhaled into the novel breath interface after a period of fasting of several hours (prior to about 390 s). While there is no trace of VG in these four exhaled breaths, there is a distinct presence of PG in the subject's breath, ranging from an average value of 59 to 67 ppbv.

Subsequently, the test subject performed a deep inhalation of the ENDS' aerosol and exhaled into the breath interface. This process was repeated ten times with about 20 s in between each repetition and is also shown in the first column of Figure 2 (red background). Remarkably, considerable puff-by-puff concentration variations are visible. This is most likely the result of individual ENDS use and inhalation manoeuvres, but could also be due to a certain degree to variations in the aerosol production of the utilised device. Either way, the findings underline the importance of puff-by-puff resolved studies for further investigations. The measured concentration range is from 5448 to 16591 ppbv and 299 to 712 ppbv in the case of VG and PG, respectively. However, the variations of the concentrations of VG and PG are correlated, as can be seen in the first column of Figure 2.

After the ten exhalations following inhalation of the aerosols of an ENDS, we recorded the washout phase of these compounds in the subject's breath. In the second column, the concentrations and the respective time frame, i.e. up to 1050 s, are shown. Note that the first high signal region in the time from approximately 666 to 680 s (red background) belongs to the series of the ten exhaled breaths after using an ENDS. In the second panel of the first row, an exponential-like decrease in the mean value of the VG concentration can be observed (yellow background).

The mean value is only 40 ppbv after 5 min. In the case of PG (second panel in the second row, yellow background), on the other hand, a fairly constant concentration can be seen, ranging from 80 to 119 ppbv. This is about twice as high as directly before the use of an ENDS.

After 87 min since the last use of an ENDS, we recorded again seven exhaled breaths. In the case of PG, see Figure 2 right panel in the bottom row (green background), the average concentration has decreased to a comparable range like before the use of an ENDS (46 to 52 ppbv). In the case of VG, see Figure 2 right panel in the top row (green background), there is hardly any concentration above the background noise level present. Since it was difficult to define borders for the calculation of the average values per exhaled breath in this case, we used the time windows determined from the PG concentration. We find average concentration values only below 5 ppbv.

Conclusion

We presented results obtained with a novel PTR-TOF-MS inlet system that enables the online analysis of ENDS mainstream aerosol and exhaled breath in real-time with high time resolution. As a first proof-of-concept, concentrations of VG and PG in exhaled breath were shown before, during and after using an ENDS. During the use of an ENDS, we find that the concentrations of both VG and PG can vary quite substantially, i.e. by a factor of about 3, which underlines the importance of puff-by-puff resolved studies.

The concentration of VG in exhaled breath decreases in an exponential-like fashion immediately after the end of the use of the ENDS. About one and a half hours after the use of the ENDS, there is hardly any trace of VG detectable. In the case of PG, we find a certain background in the exhaled breath of the subject (about 60 ppbv) before the use of the ENDS. Immediately after the end of consumption, the concentration values drop and remain at an almost constant value, which is about twice as high as in blank breath. One and a half hours later, the concentration of PG has reached about the same level as before the inhalation of the ENDS' aerosol.

With these results, we demonstrated the capability of our setup for online monitoring of ENDS inhalation and exhalation, which allows comprehensive studies to quantitatively investigate the concentrations of constituents of ENDS aerosols. Furthermore, our findings indicate that the setup is perfectly suitable for studies on the human metabolism of compounds ingested via ENDS use.

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